

Traditional Uzbek ceremonies and their impact on the economy and households

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Abstract

This paper examines the economic impact of Uzbek traditional ceremonies, such as circumcisions, weddings and funerals, on the country's economy and household spending behavior. These rituals, deeply rooted in the culture, usually demand significant spending that mostly exceeds an average family's annual income. The study has two main aims: first, to evaluate both macro and microeconomic effects of the related ceremonial expenditures over the past twenty years. Second, it explores the social expectations and governmental regulations that have shaped the financial decision-making of Uzbek households.

Findings reveal that traditional ritual parties account for a considerable portion of national expenditure, bringing prosperity to the hospitality, retail and service sectors while burdening households financially, forcing them to incur debt or rely on remittances from labor migration. Although the government has implemented measures to limit excessive spending, these regulations are often ineffective.

The study concludes that traditional ceremonies drive household debt and labor migration, thereby reinforcing spending patterns of Uzbek families. For a substantial change, a cultural shift toward modest ceremonies is important to lessen financial and social strain and promote sustainable economic practices.

Keywords: traditional ceremonies, labor migration, household debt, government regulations, ritual expenditures.

Introduction

How do century-old traditions in Uzbekistan shape the country's economy today? As a nation deeply rooted in its cultural heritage, Uzbek customs usually extend beyond mere social practices and have profound economic implications due to scale and spending. Traditional rituals which start from the birth of an individual and continue till the death reinforce social bonds and cultural values bringing communities together through collective participation, shared responsibilities, and mutual support during important life events.

The existing research examined the average cost of the three main types of rituals (circumcisions, weddings, funerals) and their connection with the labor migration of Uzbeks to Russia and Kazakhstan. However, there is a gap in the current literature as it did not consider fully economic impacts on families and did not study expenditures on a larger scale to evaluate their economic contribution to the GDP.

Therefore, this research aims to explore the economic effects, both on macroeconomic and microeconomic, of Uzbek traditions during the last two decades, examining how social expectations and government regulations influence the households' economic behaviors. Few available sources show that spending on traditional celebrations, like weddings and funerals, are several times bigger than an average family income. This paradox is examined in more detail in the analysis section of the paper, after briefly describing the most significant customs and traditions in Uzbek culture.

The specific research questions that guide this study are as follows:

- What impact do expensive customs and traditions have on the Uzbek economy and households?

- How are labor migration and overspending on rituals linked?
- How effective are government efforts to limit excessive expenditures on weddings and pre-wedding ceremonies?

Methodology

This study relies on secondary data analysis based on national statistics, international datasets (World Bank, UNDP, IOM), and prior sociological surveys. Estimates of ritual expenditures were calculated using official demographic statistics combined with inflation-adjusted cost data reported in earlier field studies. Macroeconomic impact was approximated by aggregating estimated annual spending across weddings, funerals, and circumcision ceremonies.

Uzbekistan's traditional ceremonies

Rituals in Uzbekistan and most collectivist societies, including all the four remaining countries in Central Asia, can be divided into three main domains: after-birth, weddings, and funerals, some of them differing by gender.

Main rituals

After-birth rituals for males include two important ceremonies, “*beshtik-toi*” (cradle celebration) and “*sunnat-toi*” (circumcision ceremonies), the latter of which is mandatory for Muslims. Cradle celebration (*beshtik-toi*) not only marks the birth of a child, symbolizing the family's joy and gratitude, but also sometimes includes several blessings and Aqiqah (the practice of reading Islamic prayer, *azan*, and assigning a name for the child). While for girls, after-birth

ceremonies include only the cradle celebration, which is not mandatory. Therefore, they tend to be less costly compared to those for boys, reflecting social gender hierarchy roles (Ilkhamov, 2013). This difference in expenses based on sex is part of broader societal norms of Uzbeks and many other collectivist cultures, where sons are often seen as the carriers of family legacy.

Yurevna (2022) identified the 20 practices of Uzbek weddings based on the one specific region, Namangan, and categorized them into 3 types: pre-wedding, wedding, and post-wedding ceremonies. Pre-wedding period is usually longer than the two other ones, and includes acts like getting girl's family to accept the wedding (*sovchilik*), three gift-giving (*tilla taqdi*, *paxta berdi*, *yuk berdi*) and showing off the dowry in the future rooms of the newlyweds' future home for the neighbors to see. The cultural significance of gaining the girl's family's acceptance is in strengthening family honor and establishing connections between two sides, highlighting the so-called contract of marriage. Meanwhile, practices that involve exchanging gifts demonstrate commitment on the groom's side, showing off the received dowry to the public shows the social status and expectations regarding the marriage. Post-wedding ceremonies cost comparatively low and include various significant rituals such as ceremonies that involve the introduction of the bride to the groom's relatives (*kelin salom*), where she unveils her face and receives gifts, as well as intimate gatherings attended only by women from both families to showcase the bride's attire (*challari*).

In contrast to the first two types of rituals, funerals are not associated with extreme expenses. According to customs, men should wear dark blue or black clothes, while women should only wear white head coverings along with preferably dark-colored attire. During the funeral, the national dish, plov, is provided by the family of the deceased in the name of the departed. Usually, after the meal is finished, to demonstrate deep respect and commitment, the family will not eat or

cook anything for 3 consecutive days. Additionally, Uzbeks have a custom of families engaging in acts of charity and performing public prayers in the name of the deceased, usually during the remembrance ceremonies which are held after 7 and 40 days, and first anniversary. This practice emphasizes the belief in the ongoing connection between the living and the deceased, reinforcing family bonds and honoring the memory of the departed.

Governmental measures

In the Namangan region, for some years weddings must be pre-announced some days in advance to the mahalla committee. The mahalla committee, depending on a family's economic situation, can pressure families into reducing the number of invited guests' size of the wedding (to'y) if it judges that the family cannot afford it. (Trevisani, 2016). This condition is universal for all regions across the country and has following aspects: (1)At the neighborhood level, family conditions are difficult to hide from the eyes of the mahalla and authorities find ways to be persuasive, (2) mahalla authorities have a say in how many cauldrons should be prepared in accordance with a family's income and status, the result is that even at weddings celebrated on the street the evening banquet is not served to the entire community anymore, (3)local governments put a quotas on the number of people who are allowed to enter the *to'yxonas* per wedding (restaurants or cafes) (Trevisani, 2016).

While all of these theoretically mean a possibility for the poor to save one's face in the society, in practice, measures are selectively set and rarely limit ritual expenditures. The rich with enough money to afford expensive to'y is finding ways of bypassing the law, such as organizing lavish second weddings at the not regulated cafes in the presence of certain exclusive groups of people. Trevisani 2016, rather than making celebrations more sober, the new regulations underpin

the social differentiation of the to'y, since the nature of regulation (and their uneven application) de facto supports the fragmentation of communities across rapidly consolidating social and economic boundaries between rich and poor, city and countryside.

Labor migration and ritual spending

The 2001 SDRC survey concluded that the Uzbek traditional family, specifically its head, faces four overarching life goals and obligations, apart from daily breadwinning duties (such as food, clothes, medical, etc.): 1) marrying off of children as they come of age; 2) building new houses for married children; 3) celebrating traditional lifecycle events, including weddings (*nikokh toi*), funerals (*marafa*), births (*besik toi*), circumcision of boys (*sunnat toi*); remembrance parties (*khudoyee*); and 4) providing education for children. (Ilkhamov, 2013).

For the empirical verification traditional family refers to a family with more than one generation living together. While the first two and the last spendings are common to many societies, the third objective – the custom of holding excessive, life cycle ceremonies can be considered as something unique to collectivist societies guided by conservative values and norms. Now we can assume that escaping hunger or extreme poverty is not the primary driver for migration. Indeed, Ilkhamov (2013) cited a survey conducted in 2007 among the families who sent members to Russia and Kazakhstan for work that showed that they could have survived financially and met their basic needs by working at home, without migrating.

Analysis and Discussion

How do excessive costs of traditional Uzbek rituals and ceremonies affect the country's economy and the economic behavior of the households? This research aims to establish links between labor

migration, family debt, annual spending on three main types of ceremonies, government regulations and social pressure.

Weddings

In Uzbekistan, the wedding industry significantly contributes to the economy. In Samarkand alone, there are 231 wedding halls (Zarnews, 2024) and while exact figures for the total number of halls across the country are not available, we can estimate that there are around 3,000 venues spread across the country's 12 regions and one autonomous republic. This extensive network of wedding halls supports local economies by providing employment opportunities and contribution to various sectors, including catering, decoration, and entertainment.

According to the State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan, there were 283,800 marriages in 2023. An article published five years earlier reported that the average cost of a wedding in Uzbekistan was around \$10,000, while people had an average of three children and a monthly income ranging from \$100 to \$300 (BBC, 2024). Adjusted for inflation, the average wedding cost in 2023 is approximately \$21,200 (Ilkhamov, 2013). This means the total expenditure on weddings in 2023 amounts to about \$6,016,560,000. This considerable spending stimulates economic activity by generating demand for goods and services related to weddings, thereby supporting numerous businesses and creating employment opportunities.

According to a survey conducted as a part of the "Social Development Research Cooperation Project", henceforth will be referred to as SDRC 2001, expenses in cash for the wedding party ranged from 170 to 3000 US dollars, while the monthly income of families was between 4.1 and 30.3 dollars respectively. These figures show that the latter family with 3000 dollars spent on

weddings had a ratio of expenses to per capita cash income of 473. Unfortunately, this kind of excessive expense is not unique to weddings only and applies to other types of rituals.

Funerals

Funeral ceremonies, known as *maraqas*, also contribute to the economy. With a crude death rate of 5 deaths per 1,000 people per year, there were more than 180,000 funeral ceremonies in the country in 2023 (World Bank, 2024). Since traditions within funeral ceremonies haven't seen significant changes since 2001, calculations show that the average cost, adjusted for inflation, of organizing a funeral is about \$1,100. This generates approximately \$198,000,000 in expenditure across the country. This spending supports industries such as funeral services, catering, and other related sectors.

The average annual per capita cash income in 2001 was 101 dollars, but a series of three funeral(*maraqas*) events, for example, have an average cost of 279 US dollars.

Male birth ceremonies

Male birth ceremonies are another traditional event with economic implications. Despite being the least expensive among all three, the circumcision party (*sunnat toi*) still is 1.6 times more than the average income. (Ilkhamov, 2013). With a crude birth rate of 20.9 births per 1,000 people annually, Uzbekistan sees approximately 752,400 births each year (World Bank, 2024). Considering the natural sex ratio at birth—105 boys for every 100 girls—about 51.2% of these are male, resulting

in over 385,000 male births annually. Traditional celebrations for the birth of a boy have remained largely unchanged since 2001. Adjusting the average cost of these ceremonies from \$166 in 2001 (Ilkhamov, 2013) for inflation, the current average expense is approximately \$1,100 per ceremony. This means that families across Uzbekistan collectively spend about \$423,000,000 on male birth ceremonies each year.

Overall Analysis

In total, the expenditures on weddings, funerals, and male birth ceremonies amounted to approximately \$6.64 billion over 2023. This substantial spending represented over 6% of the national economy, stimulating various sectors such as hospitality, retail, services, and entertainment. The infusion of funds into these sectors creates employment opportunities and supports small and medium-size enterprises, contributing to overall economic growth.

The estimate that on average around 30% of remittances in Uzbekistan are spent on rituals, such as weddings, religious ceremonies, and other family events, is derived from several qualitative and quantitative sources. First, qualitative research in Central Asia has highlighted that households receiving remittances often prioritize non-productive expenditures, particularly spending on culturally significant events (Marat, 2016). Reports from international organizations, such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), indicate that cultural events, including weddings and family rituals, may comprise around 20-30% of total remittances (UNDP 2016; IOM 2017). Field research conducted in regions like the Fergana Valley supports these figures, noting that up to 40% of remittances may be directed toward ceremonial expenses, depending on social and family obligations (IOM, 2017). In 2023,

the total amount of remittances to Uzbekistan was \$16.1 billion (Simple Networking Solutions, 2013–2024). Assuming that 30% of this amount funded main traditional ceremonies, the total estimate would be \$4.83 billion, or 72% of the total spending on rituals and ceremonies. However, it is important to note that not all families have the ability to send their members abroad for work, and therefore, for many families, the funding for rituals comes from other sources. The remaining 18% of the necessary funds is typically gathered through savings or taking out loans, amounting in \$1.81 billion.

These figures underscore the significant economic strain that ceremonial obligations impose on households. Families often allocate resources to these events that far exceed their financial capabilities, leading to several adverse economic consequences. Firstly, there is a high likelihood of accruing debt, as families may borrow money or sell assets to meet these social expectations. This debt can have long-term repercussions, limiting future financial opportunities and exacerbating poverty cycles. Secondly, the depletion of savings to fund ceremonies reduces the financial resilience of households, making them more vulnerable to economic shocks such as illness, job loss, or other unforeseen expenses.

Moreover, the opportunity cost associated with these expenditures is substantial. Funds directed towards ceremonial events are unavailable for investment in essential areas that could enhance the household's future earning potential and quality of life, such as education, healthcare, or entrepreneurial ventures. This diversion of resources can impede socioeconomic mobility and perpetuate a cycle of limited economic advancement.

In such circumstances, labor migration emerges as a critical strategy for households to finance these ceremonial expenses. While it provides a necessary influx of money, it also reinforces

traditional spending patterns that prioritize ceremonial expenses over long-term financial planning. Interviews with the residents of a small town in Andijan oblast in 2007 illustrate this phenomenon (Ilkhamov, 2013). While those who stayed home could provide for basic needs, they lacked the means to afford durable goods or pay for ritual celebrations. The primary motivation for migration was to fulfill strategic family priorities, particularly expenditures for life-cycle ceremonies and dowries.

Conclusion

This research aimed to explore the economic effects of Uzbek traditions during the last two decades, examining the strategies that families employed to finance the traditional ceremonies.

Expensive customs and traditions, particularly weddings, impose significant short and long-term financial strain on individual households. However, for the Uzbek economy as a whole, the long-term negative effects may outweigh the short-term boosts.

There is a clear connection between labor migration and the need to fund extravagant rituals in Uzbekistan. The financial burden imposed by ceremonial spending often leads individuals—particularly in rural and economically disadvantaged regions—to seek employment opportunities abroad. The pressure to fund lavish ceremonies often becomes the catalyst for labor migration, as one-third of remittances sent back by migrant workers are spent on covering those expenses.

The Uzbek government has implemented measures to limit excessive spending on weddings and pre-wedding ceremonies, but their effectiveness has been mixed. This limited effectiveness suggests that mere legal prohibitions may not be sufficient in curbing overspending behaviors

driven by social norms. Instead, the government may need to focus on encouraging families to hold less expensive functions through normative changes. Such initiatives could help foster a culture where modest ceremonies become socially acceptable and even desirable, reducing the financial pressures on households.

The research, however, has several limitations which must be considered in order to place the results in the appropriate perspective. Firstly, the availability of updated and robust data limited a more comprehensive analysis of economic impacts.

Secondly, this study couldn't factor in the geographical differences across Uzbekistan, as traditional rituals vary. Additionally, the costs of cultural practices may differ regionally between urban and rural areas, or in different ethnic and social groups within the country. Thus, the generalizability of the results may be constrained.

To address these limitations, future research could prioritize the collection of primary data and analyze a comprehensive economic impact of traditional Uzbek rituals and ceremonies, considering regional specificities. Conducting new surveys that encompass various regions and diverse communities within Uzbekistan would enhance the representativeness and relevance of the findings. This would allow researchers to capture contemporary economic conditions, cultural practices, and societal attitudes toward ritual spending. Moreover, comparative studies with other Central Asian countries or collectivist societies experiencing similar challenges could also be interesting to enrich the understanding of how cultural practices influence economic behaviors. Identifying common factors and successful interventions in different contexts may provide useful lessons for addressing the issue in Uzbekistan.

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